

MORPHOLOGY OF BRAIN TISSUE IN INTOXICATION PSYCHOSIS.

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Relevance of the topic: Drunkenness and intoxication psychoses are one of the understudied branches of psychiatry, where the nature of the disease so clearly raises the important question of the type of reaction of the human body to this or that damage, exogenous and endogenous interdependence and their role, that some mental diseases, syndromes and the emergence and dominance of others is manifested. Everyone knows how urgent the problem of addiction to psychoactive substances is, how much alcohol and drugs bring harm and tragedies to our lives. For example, on a global scale, premature death from alcohol accounts for 7.2% of all violent deaths. Drug poisoning is increasing day by day. The growth of illegal methadone use worldwide is due to the development of technologies that allow rapid and mass synthesis. the number of opiates detected has increased over the past three years and has been increasing at the same time. A number of amphetamine derivatives, n-methylephedrone derivatives and khakozos are poisoning the minds of young people today.

Illicit drug use is a global phenomenon that affects millions of people and has serious medical and social consequences. Information on the level and structure of drug use has prompted the development of new tools, which has prompted the need for many studies to assess the real situation in this area. Intoxication psychosis is a mental illness that occurs as a result of acute and chronic poisoning with various poisons, as well as with an overdose of narcotics or other substances, including drugs, sometimes manifested by special sensitivity to the latter.

Some researchers also call metalcogol psychoses intoxication psychoses, and data on specific morphological changes are not provided, which, in turn, makes it possible to develop specific recommendations for medical practice.

The purpose of the work: the purpose of the work is to study the morphological and histochemical changes in different parts of the brain tissue of 21 corpses brought

to the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy of the Khorezm Region from the Regional Dispensary of Mental and Nervous Diseases.

Obtained results: during scientific research, according to the results of pathologoanatomical and biopsy materials, the internal organs of 21 corpses were examined as macropreparation and micropreparation.

According to the morphological changes of the brain tissue in intoxication psychosis, the treatment practice provided an opportunity to predict the changes from the morphofunctional point of view and to prevent the expected complications.

The brain tissue material obtained during the autopsy of 21 cases of people who died in the psychiatric and drug dispensary within 5 years was used as material. Of these, 3 female and 18 male materials were taken. The prepared fragments were studied morphologically.

Obtained biopsy materials were analyzed using hematoxylin eosin, Van Gison, ShIK and Schiff methods from histochemical methods, tissue structural structures and blood vessels through morphometric tests.

Conclusion: in conclusion, it can be said that intoxication psychoses mainly occur in patients, the stress of the mother during pregnancy, the impact of infections on the immune system in childhood and its complications, the socialization and psychological development of the child, anatomical and functional deviations in the structure of the brain, mechanical effects on the brain, i.e. craniocerebral trauma or Tumors, hormone effects, as well as various somatic diseases are the cause.

In the course of the research, brain tissue material obtained at autopsy in 21 cases was organized. Among them, 3 were female and 18 were male.

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